

Incidence of bacterial blight of rice in the Punjab (Pakistan)

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Bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* is not generally found in Pakistan, but Mew et al reported its occurrence during 1976 kharif in the rice fields of Kala Shah Kaku, Punjab [IRRN 2 (1) (1977)]. In 1980 because of heavy monsoon rains and frequent windstorms, the pathogen has reappeared. Its incidence was observed

in the experimental fields of the Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, and in farmers' fields. The disease was noted on the rice varieties IR6, Palman, and Basmati 198. Infected leaf samples were examined microscopically, and the bacterial ooze at the junction of the infected and healthy parts of the cut leaves was observed.

Among the various climatic factors that favor the development of bacterial blight, temperature and humidity seem to be more important.

During July-August 1976, the amount of rainfall was 413 mm and the weather remained cloudy most of the time. The

appearance of the disease was recorded under such weather conditions. In July-August 1980, rainfall was 886.3 mm and the weather was similar to that in 1976. The disease seems to flourish in highly humid and cloudy conditions.

During 1980, windstorms frequently accompanied rain showers and the injury they caused on the leaves provided openings for the entrance of the pathogen.

During the infection period, the temperature ranged from 25 to 32 ± 1°C, which is highly conducive to the spread of the disease. ■

Fungicidal control of sheath blight

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The efficiency of fungicides applied as prophylactic and therapeutic sprays and as soil drench in the control of sheath blight disease was studied. The variety ADT31 sown in pots was fertilized with 120-6040 kg N-P-K/ha. The fungicides carbendazim (0.01%), carboxin (0.01%), Kitazin (0.02%), Panolil (0.02%), Syllit (0.02%), Mancozeb (0.02%), and Daconil (0.02%) were sprayed on the plants as protective and curative treatments. For the prophylactic treatment the fungicides were sprayed on 60-day-old plants. Two days later the plants were inoculated with the pathogen by the pinprick method (2-3 pin-pricks/plant on the leaf sheath 6-10 cm above the water level). Sclerotia were immediately applied on the pricked surface and covered with moist cotton. For the therapeutic treatment, the 60-day-old plants were inoculated; 2 days later the fungicides were sprayed. For drenching, carbendazim (0.01%), carboxin (0.01%), wet Ceresan (0.01%), and PCNB (0.01%) were applied to the soil of the 60-day-old plants immediately after inoculation. The control was plants inoculated with the pathogen but not protected with fungicides. Each treatment had three replications. Ten days after inoculation, disease incidence was recorded and disease severity (0-9

Table 1. Percentage of disease index (PDI) when fungicides were applied as prophylactic and therapeutic sprays. Coimbatore, India.

Fungicide sprayed	PDI value ^a	
	Prophy-lactic spray	Thera-peutic spray
Carbendazim (0.01%)	24.92	25.49
Carboxin (0.01%)	26.08	27.08
Kitazin (0.01%)	27.09	28.09
Panolil (0.027%)	49.07	49.49
Syllit (0.02%)	42.67	44.81
Mancozeb (0.02%)	49.49	50.77
Daconil (0.02%)	40.51	40.51
Control (no fungicide)	54.75	55.66

^aTransformed values. Mean of 3 replications.

S.E.D. = 1.30 1.06

C.D. = 2.80 2.28

(P = 0.05% level)

Table 2. Percentage of disease index (PDI) when fungicides were applied as soil drench. Coimbatore, India.

Fungicide used for drenching	PDI value ^a
Carbendazim (0.01%)	27.72
Carboxin (0.01%)	27.72
Wet Ceresan (0.01%)	29.17
PCNB (0.01%)	28.47
Control (no fungicide)	58.33

^aTransformed values. Mean of 3 replications.

S.E.D. = 1.48; C.D. = 3.23 at P = 0.05% level.

scale) was determined. The percentage of the disease index (PDI) was determined:

$$PDI = \frac{\text{total ratings} \times 100}{\text{no. of tillers} \times \text{maximum grade}}$$

Both as prophylactic and therapeutic spray, carbendazim, carboxin, and Kitazin most effectively controlled the

disease (Table 1). As soil drench, carbendazim, carboxin, wet Ceresan, and PCNB were equally effective (Table 2). Both carbendazim and carboxin, however, were effective as a spray and as a drench. ■

Effect of nitrogen and spacing on sheath blight incidence in rice

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In a fertilization-spacing trial conducted during 1979 kuruvai, the incidence of sheath blight was assessed. There were 4 spacings (10 x 10, 20 x 20, 30 x 30, and 40 x 40 cm) and 4 levels of nitrogen (0, 50, 100, and 200 kg/ha) applied as full basal, 2 splits (75 + 25%), 3 splits (50 + 25 + 25%), and 4 splits (40 + 20 + 20 + 20%). Phosphorus and potassium were applied at 98% sufficiency level of the field. Data on sheath blight incidence are in the table.

With zero nitrogen, there was no disease incidence at all spacings.

With 50 kg N/ha, disease incidence ranged from 16.2 to 21.6% for the 10- x 10-cm spacing and 1.8 to 2.7% for 20 x 20 cm. No incidence was noted at the 30- x 30- and 40- x 40-cm spacings. With 100 kg N/ha, disease incidence was 49.5-59.4% for the 10- x 10-cm spacing, 4.5-6.3% for 20 x 20 cm and only 0.7-1.0% at 30 x 30 and 40 x 40 cm.

With 200 kg N/ha, disease incidence was 53.1-60.3% for the 10-x 10-cm.

spacing 5.4-8.1% for 20 x 20 cm, and only 0.7-1.6% for 30 x 30 and 40 x 40 cm.

At the 10- x 10-cm spacing the increase in disease incidence was 171.1% from N₅₀ to N₁₀₀ but only 7.6% from

N₁₀₀ to N₂₀₀.

At the 20- x 20-cm spacing the increase in disease incidence was 137.4% from N₅₀ to N₁₀₀ and 29.1% from N₁₀₀ to N₂₀₀. ■

Data on sheath blight incidence in Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Sheath blight incidence (%) at spacing of			
	10 x 10 cm	20 x 20 cm	30 x 30 cm	40 x 40 cm
N ₀ – Full basal	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 2 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 3 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 4 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₅₀ – Full basal	16.2	2.7	–	–
N ₅₀ – 2 splits	21.6	1.8	–	–
N ₅₀ – 3 splits	19.8	2.6	–	–
N ₅₀ – 4 splits	20.7	2.0	–	–
N ₁₀₀ – Full basal	51.3	4.5	0.9	0.8
N ₁₀₀ – 2 splits	59.4	5.4	0.8	1.0
N ₁₀₀ – 3 splits	52.2	6.3	0.8	0.9
N ₁₀₀ – 4 splits	49.5	5.4	0.7	0.8
N ₂₀₀ – Full basal	58.5	8.1	0.9	1.1
N ₂₀₀ – 2 splits	56.7	7.2	0.8	0.7
N ₂₀₀ – 3 splits	60.3	5.4	1.6	0.9
N ₂₀₀ – 4 splits	53.1	7.2	0.9	0.8

Rice blast — races or virulence frequencies?

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A recent article on races of *Pyricularia oryzae* raises several interesting questions about the current state of understanding of the population genetics and dynamics of the pathogen (Wu, H. K. 1979. Rice blast disease in Taiwan — Race and variety resistance. Tech. Bull. ASPAC Food Fert. Tech. Cent. 48.).

The author advocated the use of the international differential set of rice varieties to monitor changes in the racial composition of blast in Taiwan. He concluded that “race distribution was stable” because the predominant races in 1975-78 were similar to those in 1966.

This conclusion is not necessarily valid because the race frequencies studied involved only the characterization of virulence frequencies corresponding to those of the international differentials. Substantial changes in the racial composition in Taiwan could conceivably have been detected if relevant local varieties had been used as differentials.

The author also commented that “a lot of labor would be saved” if the international differentials were used instead of 12-16 local differentials. Although the labor saving is undeniable, much important information might be lost. It seems more logical to concentrate in the future on the frequencies of relevant pathogen genes rather than on frequencies of largely irrelevant genotypes.

The paper further contended that the disease severity on a rice variety was determined by the “number of its existing virulent races.” A more accurate statement may be that disease severity is determined by the frequency of the corresponding virulence in the pathogen population. This virulence may be present in one or many races. That there is often a direct correlation between the number of virulent races (as determined by an arbitrary set of differentials) that can attack a variety and its susceptibility is merely a statistical artifact of the race concept.

If a variety is susceptible, it may be assumed that the corresponding virulence is high in frequency. There is then a correspondingly high probability

of it being combined with other virulences in the pathogen population. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India

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References to large-scale occurrence of viral and mycoplasmal diseases on rice have lately been frequent. During routine field visits at the Agricultural Experimental Farm of Annamalai University, the authors detected diseased and stunted plants (culture ARC5752 from IRRRI). The leaves were ragged and serrated, and vein-swelling was marked on the outer surface of the leaf sheath. Flag leaves were small, twisted, and malformed and showed incomplete emergence. Panicle emergence was incomplete and panicles bore mostly chaffy grains. Most of the tillers were branched and produced many panicles. Flowering was delayed and the diseased plant was totally unproductive.

With those characteristic symptoms the disease was suspected to be ragged stunt as described by K.C. Ling [IRRN 2(5) (1977): 6-7]. The disease is reported for the first time from this part of India; however, its occurrence in Coimbatore has been mentioned in a publication of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. The disease is transmitted and spread by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. As the BPH population is increasing in the Cauvery delta, large-scale recurrence of the disease is possible. Hence, suitable prophylactic control measures will be taken up to reduce the BPH populations. ■

Studies on udbatta disease in Karnataka, India

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Udbatta disease caused by *Ephelis oryzae* has occurred in Karnataka State for more than three decades and caused